

Iron(III), Ruthenium(III), Rhodium(III), Palladium(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with *N*-(α -Pyridyl)furfural-2-aldehyde Thiosemicarbazone and *N*-(α -Pyridyl)thiophene-2-aldehyde Thiosemicarbazone

C. L. JAIN*, P. N. MUNDLEY and R. BAJAJ

Department of Chemistry, M. M. H. College, Ghaziabad-201 001

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In view of the pharmacological importance of *d*-metal complexes with heterocyclic thiosemicarbazones, we report herein the synthesis and characterisation of *N*-(α -pyridyl)furfural-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (PFI) and *N*-(α -pyridyl)thiophene-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (PTT). Their complexes with Fe^{III}, Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Pd^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} are isolated and characterised by chemical analysis, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility, ligand field, Mössbauer and infrared spectral studies in order to evaluate the stereochemistry of the ligands around these metal ions.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic moment data at 298 K (5.91 and 5.98 B.M.), isomer shift (0.36 and 0.38 mm s⁻¹ at 298 K and 0.43 and 0.44 mm s⁻¹ at 78 K) and quadrupole splitting (0.74 and 0.75 mm s⁻¹ at 298 K and 0.79 and 0.78 mm s⁻¹ at 78 K) data of the Fe^{III} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, reveal high-spin distorted octahedral stereochemistry around the Mössbauer atom. The absorption bands of the Fe^{III} complexes observed at 13 520, 17 200, 23 750, 28 170 and 37 800 cm⁻¹ (PFT complex) and 14 060, 19 650, 25 400, 30 500 and 42 000 cm⁻¹ (PTT complex) are tentatively assigned¹ to (⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}) = Dq; (⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}); t_{2g} → n* ; n → e_g and n → n* transitions respectively. The calculated values of B₃₅ (1 229 and 1 278 cm⁻¹); β₃₅ (0.94 and 0.98), F₂ (94.63 and 98.42 kK), F₄ (61.94 and 64.22 kK) and n → n* (38.40 and 41.84 kK) from the Fe^{III} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, conclude¹ high-spin distorted octahedral stereochemistry. The increased values of F₂ and F₄ in comparison to free-ion values of 80.93 and 50.27 kK

respectively, may be considered due to expanded radial function of the *d*-electrons after complexation. The accuracy of the present assignments is also supported by the calculated values of n → n*, which are in good agreement with the observed values.

The absorption bands of the Ru^{III} complexes observed at 20 700 (with PFT) and 18 780 cm⁻¹ (with PTT) are assigned² to ²T_{1g} → ²A_{2g} transition. The two other bands at 16 500 and 22 700 cm⁻¹ (with PFT) and 14 100 and 21 200 cm⁻¹ (with PTT), if assigned² to two spin-forbidden transitions, then the separation energy between them would correspond to 8B. The values of 10Dq are calculated from the relation (Dq/B) = 5.1. The values of effective magnetic moment at 301 K (1.51 and 1.54 B.M.), 10 Dq (39 252 and 41 437 cm⁻¹) and B (775.0 and 812.5 cm⁻¹) for the Ru^{III} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, correspond to one unpaired electron indicating distorted octahedral stereochemistry.

For the Rh^{III} complexes with PFT and PTT, the values of magnetic moment (0.30 and 0.30 B.M.) and the absorption bands observed at 13 750, 21 780, 30 760 and 41 480 cm⁻¹ (PFT complex) and 14 500, 22 300, 32 750 and 44 200 cm⁻¹ (PTT complex) are assigned³ to spin-allowed transitions, ¹A_{1g} → ³T_{1g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} (ν₁) and ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} (ν₂) respectively, following (t_{2g})⁵(e_g)¹ configuration. The fourth band beyond 40 000 cm⁻¹ is of charge transfer type, indicating distorted octahedral stereochemistry around Rh^{III} ion with diamagnetic nature of the complexes.

The calculated values of ν₂/ν₁ (1.41 and 1.46), B (561.2 and 653.1 cm⁻¹), β (0.77 and 0.90), 10 Dq or Δ (22 838 and 23 340 cm⁻¹), F₂ (1 646 and 1 625 cm⁻¹), F₄ (1 027 and 1 040 cm⁻¹), L.F.S.E. (27.38 and 28.35 kcal mol⁻¹) and effective cationic charge

z^2 (1.46 and 2.29) of the Rh^{III} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, suggest³ distorted octahedral stereochemistry around Rh^{III} ion with diamagnetic nature of the complexes. The reduced values of B obtained in comparison to free-ion value (720 cm^{-1}), are associated to considerable orbital overlap with an increased covalency in the metal-ligand σ -bond as well as reduced effective cationic charge (z^*).

For the Pd^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT, the values of magnetic moment at 302 K (0.38 and 0.35 B.M.) and the absorption bands observed at 18 750, 21 000, 28 600, 35 250 and 47 000 cm^{-1} (PFT complex) and 18 900, 22 800, 29 650, 36 700 and 47 250 cm^{-1} (PTT complex) are assigned⁴ to spin-allowed transitions, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g} = (\Delta_1 - C)$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g} = (\Delta_1 + \Delta_2 + 4B + C)$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_g = \Delta_1 + \Delta_2 + \Delta_3 + (3B + C)$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2u} - a^1E_u$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow b^1E_u$ respectively. The higher energy bands around 35 000 and 47 000 cm^{-1} are attributed to intra-ligand charge transfer transition. The calculated values of ligand field parameters, Δ_1 (22 250 and 22 400 cm^{-1}), Δ_2 (4 250 and 5 900 cm^{-1}), Δ_3 (7 100 and 6 350 cm^{-1}) and L.F.S.E. (76.09 and 76.61 kcal mol^{-1}) for the Pd^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, are attributed⁴ to the square-planer geometry around Pd^{II} ion with diamagnetic nature of the complexes.

For the Co^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT, the magnetic moment at 301 K (5.07 and 4.99 B.M.) and the three spin-allowed bands observed at 8 650, 18 620 and 20 800 cm^{-1} (PFT complex) and 9 750, 18 900 and 21 550 cm^{-1} (PTT complex) are tentatively assigned⁵ to $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions respectively. The values of $10Dq$ (9 970 and 9 150 cm^{-1}), B (898.0 and 869.0 cm^{-1}), β (0.80 and 0.77), ν_3/ν_1 (2.40 and 2.21) and ν_2/ν_1 (2.15 and 1.93) for the Co^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, suggest⁶ tetragonally distorted octahedral geometry of the Co^{II} complexes.

For the Ni^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT, the magnetic moment at 301 K (2.92 and 3.02 B.M.) and three sharp absorptions observed at 9 750, 15 300 and 26 950 cm^{-1} (PFT complex) and 9 750, 15 500 and 27 000 cm^{-1} (PTT complex) are tentatively assigned³ to $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions respectively. In addition to these bands, a weak shoulder (12 300 and 12 450 cm^{-1}) for the Ni^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively (free-ion value 1 040 cm^{-1}), suggest covalent character in the bonds. The ratios ν_2/ν_1 (1.56 and 1.58) and ν_3/ν_1 (1.75 and 1.74) observed for these Ni^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, for octahedral complexes, are greater than the usual range ~ 1.50 and ~ 1.70 respectively. These increased values might be assigned to the distortion from octahedral geometry with cubic field. The amount of splitting in ν_1 band is taken as a measure of the degree of distortion, i.e. (35/4) Dt . The probable assignments to split components⁶ can be given as $^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3E_g$ for 9 500 cm^{-1} and $^3B_{1g} \rightarrow ^3B_{2g}$ for 12 000 cm^{-1} . The

values of crystal field radial parameters, viz. Dt (291.4 and 08.5 cm^{-1}), $Dq.z^2$ (650 and 705 cm^{-1}), $Dq.xy$ (1 200 and 1 245 cm^{-1}), ratio of NSH (normalised spherical harmonic Hamiltonian) parameters, DT/DQ (0.186 and 0.176) and L.F.S.E. (33.34 and 33.39 kcal mol^{-1}) calculated for the Ni^{II} complexes with PFT and PTT respectively, clearly ascertain^{3,8} distorted octahedral stereochemistry of the Ni^{II} complexes.

The sharp absorption bands observed at 1 620 and 1 600 cm^{-1} in the free ligands PFT and PTT respectively, can be attributed to $\nu_{C=N}$ of imine-N, which on coordination shifted towards higher wavenumber by 15–25 cm^{-1} , indicating³ involvement of imino-N in coordination. Pyridinic nitrogen-metal bond is due to blue-shift of sharp absorption bands, viz. 1 590, 1 560 cm^{-1} (PFT) and 1 540 and 1 500 cm^{-1} (PTT) in free ligand assigned³ to symmetric and anti-symmetric ($\nu_{C=C} + \nu_{C=N}$) frequencies due to pyridine ring, while pyridine ring breathing modes observed at 1 085 and 1 075 cm^{-1} (PFT) and 1 085 and 1 070 cm^{-1} (PTT) show red-shift. On complexation, the sharp absorption bands observed in the free ligands at 825 and 810 cm^{-1} (PFT) and 825 and 820 cm^{-1} (PTT) assigned^{3,7} to $\nu_{C=S}$, shifted to lower wavenumber with reduced intensity which indicates involvement of thioketo-S in coordination. Strong bands observed at 610 and 595 cm^{-1} (PFT) assigned⁷ to furan ring deformation modes, show 15–25 cm^{-1} red-shift on complexation, indicating metal-ligand bonding through furfuryl oxygen. The strong bands observed at 640 and 572 cm^{-1} and 490 and 471 cm^{-1} (PTT) assigned⁷ to thiophene ring (C=C) out-of-plane and (C-S-C) in-plane bending modes respectively, also show 15–20 cm^{-1} red-shift indicating involvement of thiophene-S in coordination. In the Ni^{II} -ammonia complexes, medium broad bands observed at 3 240, 3 190 and 1 180 cm^{-1} (PFT complex) and 3 280, 3 160 and 1 215 cm^{-1} (PTT complex) are assigned to ν_a (NH_2), ν_s (NH_3) and δ_s (HNH) respectively. In all of the present complexes, the medium to weak bands in the far-ir region, viz. 550–520, 454–427, 370–365 and 325–307 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned³ to ν (M-imine-N), ν (M-thioketo-S), ν (M-Cl) and ν (M-pyridinic-N) respectively, suggesting teradentate nature of the ligands PFT and PTT during complexation.

Experimental

PFT ($C_{11}H_{10}N_4SO$) and PTT ($C_{11}H_{10}N_4S_2$) were prepared by adding furfural-2-aldehyde/thiophene-2-aldehyde (0.1 mol) with continuous stirring to a hot ethanolic solution (50 ml) of α -pyridylthiosemicarbazide⁸ ($(C_5H_4N)NHC(=S)NH.NH_2$, $C_6H_8N_4S$; 0.1 mol). The buff-brown (PFT) and pale yellow (PTT) solids were washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol. Both the tlc-pure compounds were found sufficiently active against *Bacillusceous*. Average zone of inhibition from ethanolic solution (200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) of PFT and

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd. (Colour)	M.p./Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)				Mol. cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
			C	S	Cl*	M*	
1.	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{SO}$ (Buff brown) (PFT)	178	55.42 (55.66)	13.54 (13.01)	22.25 (27.76)	4.17 (4.06)	—
2.	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$ (Pale yellow) (PTT)	159.5	50.58 (50.38)	24.62 (24.42)	21.05 (21.37)	3.72 (3.82)	—
3.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{PFT})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (Reddish brown)	173	32.10 (32.32)	8.46 (7.84)	26.35 (26.08)	13.93 (13.67)	115.2
4.	$[\text{Fe}(\text{PTT})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (Light brown)	156	31.24 (31.11)	14.61 (15.08)	25.27 (25.09)	13.35 (13.16)	107.5
5.	$[\text{Ru}(\text{PFT})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (Dark violet)	161	28.85 (29.01)	7.46 (7.05)	23.72 (23.47)	22.04 (22.28)	131.2
6.	$[\text{Ru}(\text{PTT})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (Blackish violet)	173	28.31 (28.07)	13.24 (13.61)	21.96 (22.64)	22.03 (21.62)	107.1
7.	$[\text{Rh}(\text{PFT})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (Reddish brown)	167	28.35 (28.98)	6.82 (7.03)	23.68 (23.38)	22.43 (22.60)	127.0
8.	$[\text{Rh}(\text{PTT})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ (Reddish yellow)	171	28.62 (28.00)	13.22 (13.57)	22.12 (22.59)	22.17 (21.82)	112.4
9.	$[\text{Pd}(\text{PFT})]\text{Cl}_2$ (Buff yellow)	154	30.85 (31.18)	7.94 (7.56)	16.42 (16.77)	25.76 (25.13)	181.5
10.	$[\text{Pd}(\text{PTT})](\text{CN})_2$ (Grayish yellow)	158	36.75 (37.11)	14.84 (15.22)	—	26.55 (25.31)	170.05
11.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{PFT})(\text{NH}_3)_2]$ (Brown)	155	38.68 (38.97)	9.16 (9.44)	—	17.60 (17.33)	19.25
12.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{PTT})(\text{NH}_3)_2]$ (Brownish yellow)	165	32.62 (32.29)	15.94 (15.65)	—	14.38 (14.19)	23.71
13.	$[\text{Co}(\text{PFT})\text{Cl}_2]$ (Dark red)	148	35.47 (35.10)	8.22 (8.51)	18.46 (18.88)	15.31 (15.69)	15.73
14.	$[\text{Co}(\text{PTT})(\text{NO}_2)_2]$ (Light brown)	150	29.93 (29.66)	14.11 (14.38)	—	13.64 (13.25)	21.55

*For PFT and PTT, the data indicate N and H analyses instead of Cl and M.

PTT were observed as 13.95 and 12.38 mm respectively. The ^1H nmr spectra (DMSO-d_6) were recorded on a TESLA-BS-467 spectrometer and chemical shifts(s) being downfields from TMS as internal reference. The NH proton is bonded to the unsaturated nuclei and therefore it appears at the lowest field at 10.12 (PFT) and 9.98 ppm (PTT). Sharp doublets observed at 8.1 and 8.22 (PFT) and 8.22 and 8.34 ppm (PTT) are assigned⁹ to heterocyclic pyridine ring (in PFT) and pyridine ring (in PTT) appear as singlet resonance at δ 2.5 and 2.34 respectively.

All the complexes with PFT and PTT were prepared by following M : L (1 : 1) stoichiometry. Cyano and ammonio derivatives were prepared by using ethanolic NaCN and ethanolic ammonia respectively. Ionic chloride and total chloride ions were estimated as described earlier⁸ and relevant data (Table 1) were found in good agreement to the calculated values. The tlc-pure complexes were found insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in methanol, DMF and DMSO. Electrolytic conductance values for the complexes in 10^{-3} M DMF were observed in the region 15.73–23.71, 107.10–131.2 and 170.50–181.50 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating non-electrolytic, uni-univalent and uni-divalent nature

of the complexes respectively. Mössbauer spectra of the Fe^{III} complexes were recorded on a ECT MBS-35 Mössbauer spectrometer (National Physical Laboratory, New Delhi) at 298 and 78 K using constant acceleration, operating in a multiscalar mode with time operated electrodynamic device and using ^{57}Co as source. $\text{Na}_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used as calibrant and liquid air for spectra at 78 K.

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